

COVID-19 Patient Report

Primary and Secondary Healthcare Department
Government of the Punjab

Provincial Public Health Referral Laboratory (Punjab Aids Control Program),
Lahore

PATIENT DETAILS

Sample No:

2642051

Patient Name: Ayesha Tariq
Father/Husband Name:
Address: Hno 481 F- block johar town
Age: 34
First Report: Detected
Patient ID 2814517

Registration Date: 29-12-2020
Sample BarCode 4345495
CNIC: 33302-1112069-6
Contact No: 0336-0495413
Sample Sent To: PRL (PACP)
Center:
Lab ID 2642051
Result Date 12/30/2020 4:49:33 AM

COVID-19 PCR TEST RESULT

Report Status:

Detected

Specimen(s):

Throat Swab / Nasopharyngeal Swab

Description:

The test was performed on Roche's fully automated Cobas system (FDA, CE-IVD), intended for the qualitative dual target (ORF1ab/N Gene) detection of SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19 disease, in nasopharyngeal and oropharyngeal swab samples from patients (who meet COVID-19 clinical and/or epidemiological criteria for testing) with internal and external positive controls.

**Comments/
Recommendation:**

- On testing with Real Time RT-PCR panel, if the sample is negative for the Novel Corona Virus (COVID-19) in view of the recent travel and contact history; we may contact you for follow up regarding your general health.
- The result must be interpreted along with clinical observation, patient history and epidemiology information.

Registered By

Electronically Verified Report. No Signature Required

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